

Evaluation of the factors associated with Breastfeeding duration among Antenatal care Mothers at Rakai Hospital, Rakai District

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ABSTRACT

Breast feeding has numerous benefits for both the mother and the child including saving lives, improving child health among others. Despite the numerous known benefits of breast feeding, exclusive breast feeding among children under six months has remained below the 50% target of the World Health Assembly. The study was aimed at determining the duration and factors associated with breast feeding among mothers attending antenatal care (ANC) at Rakai District Hospital. The study was cross-sectional involving administration of questionnaires to 112 mothers attending ANC at Rakai District Hospital. 20.5% of the participants breastfeed their babies immediately, while 33.0% breastfeed after one hour. 58.0% of the participant's breastfed exclusively for six months, 18.6% breast fed for less than six months. However, among those who breastfeed generally, 25.9% breast fed for 6-12 months, and 21.4% breastfed for 1-2 years. 90.1% of the mothers who had knowledge on exclusive breastfeeding and overall general breastfeeding, of whom 73.2% had attended ANC during pregnancy. Most of the mothers who breast fed had parity of greater than seven (32.1%), and had attained primary level education (41, 1%). The study shows that most mothers exclusively breastfed their babies for a period of less than six months, and overall breast feeding for less than two years. In this study the duration of exclusive breastfeeding and overall breastfeeding was directly associated with parity, maternal age, education level, antenatal service and knowledge of mothers on breastfeeding.

Keywords: Breast milk, breastfeeding, mothers, Uganda

INTRODUCTION

Breastfeeding is the process of feeding infants on milk from human breasts directly by suckling or indirectly through feeding bottles [1]. The breast milk provides the baby with nutrients needed for normal health, growth and development [2]. The Breast milk provides required nutrients to infants, the human milk is endogenous nutrient store contains all nutrients [2]. It provides all the energy and nutrients that is needed for growth and development for the first months of life up to two years of age [3-6].

Breastfeeding through suckling builds a strong unbreakable bond between the mother and the child for life. The practice of breastfeeding also protects mothers against breast cancer, ovarian cancer and

used as natural method of family planning [2].

Breastfeeding for a period of two years is more cost-effective than the alternative method of feeding the baby particularly in the first six months [1]. Exclusive breastfeeding is recommended as the main source of nutrients for babies the first six months [7-10]. Between six months to two years old it is recommended that mothers could use other supplemental source such as water, other liquids or solid baby food to feed their babies along with breastfeeding [1, 11].

Adequate nutrition at the stage of infant and early childhood is essential to insure the growth, health and development of the children to their full potential [2, 12]. Sub-optimal breastfeeding is

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responsible for the death of 1.4 million children and the disability of 44 million globally [13]. Therefore, it has been recommended that all women should breastfeed their infants exclusively in the first six months and subsequently with supplementary feeding for 2 years for optimal growth and development [14]. The World Health Organization and UNICEF had launched several programs like the baby friendly hospital initiative and the International Code of Marketing of Breast Milk Substitutes in order to protect, remote and support breastfeeding in response to persistent decline in the rate of breast feeding globally [14].

The maternal benefits of breastfeeding include more rapid uterine involution, delayed ovulation, and decreased rates of breast and ovarian cancers [15]. For families, breastfeeding provides a readily available food source for the infant; a healthier infant is less stressed for the family and as there are no wasteful by-products, breastfeeding is ecologically sound [8, 9, 16, 17, 18]. Orphans child is more likely to die before reach age of two years than child whose mother is alive [2]. The rate of breastfeeding is reported to be rising by 2% worldwide [19]. The health people objectives for 2020, has a target to increase the percentage of infants who are breastfeeding from 49%, by 2020 to 81.9% for children who ever breastfeed, 60.6% for children who breastfed for six months, 34.1% for children who breastfeed for

twelve months, 46.6% for children who breastfeed exclusively for three months and 25.5% for children who exclusively breastfed for six months [19].

In Sub-Saharan African countries exclusive breastfeeding rate for six months is about 30%, 47% in Ethiopia, 13% in Kenya and 50% in Tanzania [14]. Exclusive breastfeeding and overall breastfeeding is affected by several factors including the race, maternal age, maternal occupation, parent's educational level, social-economic status, insufficient milk supply, infant health problems, maternal obesity, smoking, parity, method of delivery, maternal interest, social culture, and lack of knowledge [20].

As part of Integrated Management of Childhood illness (IMCI) and Baby friendly Hospital Initiatives (BFHI), breastfeeding has been promoted for more than ten years [21]. These initiatives are based on comprehensive research documenting the benefits of breastfeeding on infant mortality and morbidity [22]. However, even with the current knowledge about the benefits of breastfeeding, breastfeeding rates remain low with high infant mortality rates [23]. Uganda Demographic and Health reports (UDHRs) found 50% of infants exclusively breastfed under 6 months based on 24hr recall with a median duration of three months [24]. In Uganda, peer support has been tried as a tool to increase the rates of breastfeeding [25].

METHODOLOGY

Study Design

The study was cross-sectional involving the use of questionnaires to the mothers attending ANC at Rakai District Hospital.

Study Area

The study was conducted at ANC Rakai District Hospital, South Central Uganda.

Study Population

The study involved mothers attending ANC at Rakai District Hospital for the period of May and June, 2017.

Sampling Method

The study sample was obtained by systematic random sampling method since every participant visited the ANC clinic at time of convenience.

Sample Size Determination

The sample of size was obtained using Yamane, (1967) method [26].

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

$$1 + N(e^2)$$

Where: n= the desired sample size
N= is the total number of mothers attending ANC at the time the study (155) was conducted.

e = the sampling error (0.05)

$$n = \frac{155}{1 + 155(0.05^2)}$$

n = 112 participants

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Inclusion and Exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

Mothers who already delivered their babies, at least one parity, and those with a child who was below two years old were considered in the study.

Exclusion Criteria in the study

Prime gravidas and mothers with a child with any kind of malformations. Mothers with children who were above two years.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was done manually by counting, tallying and using a simple electronic calculator.

A total of 112 mothers participated in the study, conducted for two months of May and June, 2017. Majority of the participants (31.5%) were aged between 35-44 years of age. Most of the participants (50%) were married. A greater proportion

Ethical Considerations

The research proposal was approved by the School of Allied Health Sciences and Community Health before its conduction. Introductory letter was then obtained from the School.

Permission was also sought from the administration of Rakai District Hospital before the study.

Informed consent was obtained from each participant before the interview, participant assured of confidentiality.

RESULTS

(43.8%) had attained primary level education. The majority of the participants (46.5%) had small scale businesses. 57.1% of the participants were Baganda and also most of them (39.3%) were Catholics. (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of study participants

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	No. of mothers breast feeding	% of mothers breast feeding
Age				
15-24	22	19.6	17	77.3
25-34	30	26.8	27	90.0
35-44	35	31.5	32	91.4
>45	25	22.3	25	100.0
Total	112	100	101	
Marital status				
Single	43	38.4	39	90.7
Married	56	50	53	94.6
Divorced	5	4.5	2	40.0
Widow	8	7.1	4	50.0
Education level				
Primary	49	43.8	46	93.9
Secondary	32	28.6	30	93.8
Tertiary	11	9.8	11	100.0
None	20	17.9	16	80.0
Occupational status				
Casual labour	15	13.4	13	86.7
Civil servant	35	31.3	31	88.6
Small scale business	52	46.4	50	96.2
House wife	40	35.7	37	92.5
Tribe				
Baganda	64	57.1	60	93.8
Banyankole	40	35.7	37	92.5
Banyoro	3	2.7	2	66.7
Others	5	4.5	3	60.0
Religion				
Muslim	25	22.3	23	92.0
Catholic	44	39.3	40	90.9
Protestant	28	25	24	85.7
Adventist	10	8.9	9	90.0
Others	5	4.5	5	100.0

The majority of the participants (33.0%) reported to have breast fed their babies

after an hour post birth, but those who breast fed their babies within an hour after

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birth were 20.5% (Table 2). Most of the participants (58.0%) also exclusively breast fed their babies for six months. The

majority of the respondents (80.3%) breast feed their babies only within a period of two years from birth.

Table 2: Timing and duration of breast feeding among mothers

Variable	Frequency	Percentage %
Time of breastfeeding		
Immediately after birth	23	20.5
After 1 hour	37	33.0
After 2 hours	18	16.1
After 1 day	6	5.4
Others	28	25
Duration of exclusive breastfeeding		
<6 months	21	18.6
6 months	65	58.0
>6 months	12	10.7
None	14	12.5
Length of breast feeding		
1-6 months	37	33
6-12 months	29	25.9
1-2 years	24	21.4
>2 years	5	4.5
Others	17	15.2

The majority of the participants (33.0%) reported to have breast fed their babies after an hour post birth, but those who breast fed their babies within an hour after birth were 20.5% and mothers of more than six parities 43.5% breastfed their babies immediately. The data also indicated that mothers of one to two parity (33.3%) breastfed their babies one day post-delivery (Table 3). The study also showed that most mothers (58.0%) breastfeed their babies exclusively for six months and mothers of seven parities and above (38.5%) breastfed their babies exclusively. However, 18.6% of the mothers breastfeed their babies for less than 6 months of which (33.3%) were of 5-6 parity and also

10.7% breastfeed exclusively for more than 6 months and 33.3% were mothers of seven and above parity.

Majority of mothers 25.9% breastfed their babies for 6-12 months and 31.0% were 1-2 parity and those who breastfeed for 1-2 years were 21.4% and majority were of 7 and above parity 58.3%. Most mothers breastfeed for 1-6 months 33% and mothers of 1-2 parity 35.1% breastfeed for this period. However, those who breastfed for 6 months to one year 25.9%, majority were 1-2 parity mothers 31.0% and those who breast fed for 1-2 years 21.4% and most of them seven and above parity mothers 58.3% breastfed for this period and for 4.5% mothers breastfed beyond 2 years.

Table 3: Parity and duration of breast feeding

Variable	Breast feeding		Parity			
	Frequency	Percentage	1-2	3-4	5-6	≥7
Time of breastfeeding						
Immediately after birth	23	20.5	3(13.4%)	3(13.4%)	7(30.4%)	10(43.5%)
Within 1 hour	37	33.0	10(27.0%)	5(13.5%)	5(13.5%)	13(31.5%)
After 2 hours	18	16.1	8(44.4%)	2(11.1%)	3(16.7)	5(27.8%)
After 1 day	6	5.4	2(33.3%)	0	1(6.7%)	0
Others	28	25	9(32.4%)	6(21.4%)	5(17.5%)	8(28.6%)
	112	100	29	16	21	36
Duration of exclusive breastfeeding						
<6 months	21	18.6	7(33.3%)	3(14.3%)	2(9.5%)	5(23.8%)
6 months	65	58.0	10(15.4%)	11(16.9%)	15(23.1%)	25(38.5%)
>6 months	12	10.7	3(25%)	2(16.7%)	1(8.3%)	4(33.3%)
None	14	12.5	9(64.2)	0	3(21.4%)	2(14.2%)
Length of breast feeding						
1-6 months	37	33	13(35.1%)	5(13.5%)	5(13.5%)	7(18.9%)
6-12 months	29	25.9	9(31.0%)	7(24.1%)	8(27.6%)	5(17.2%)
1-2 years	24	21.4	5(20.8%)	1(4.7%)	4(16.7%)	14(58.3%)
>2 years	5	4.5	0	2(40%)	2(40%)	1(20%)
Others	17	15.2	2(11.8%)	0	2(11.8%)	4(23.5%)

The study shows that (20.5%) of the mothers breastfeed their babies immediately of which (91.3%) had knowledge on importance of breastfeeding, (82.6%) had adequate knowledge on breastfeeding and (73.9%) attained their knowledge from ANC counseling. However, majority (33.3%) breastfed their babies after one hour of which (94.4%) had adequate knowledge on breastfeeding, (86.5%) and 11.1% had attained it from ANC counseling. The study also shows that (18.6%) of the mothers breastfed for less than six months exclusively of which (85.7%) had knowledge on breastfeeding importance and (42.8%) attained the knowledge from ANC. Among those who breastfed for 6months exclusively (58.0%), many of

them (96.9%) had knowledge on importance of breastfeeding and (93.3%) of the mothers had adequate knowledge about breastfeeding. The study also shows that majority of the mothers (33.0%) breastfed their babies for 1-6months of which 89.1% had adequate knowledge on breastfeeding and 54.1% had knowledge on importance of breastfeeding. However, among those who breastfed for 6-12months 25.9% of which 96.6% had knowledge on importance of breastfeeding and 75.6% had attained it from ANC counseling. Among those who breastfed for 1-2years 21.4% of which 95.5% had knowledge on importance of breastfeeding and 79.2% had attained it from ANC counseling. (Table 4).

Table 4: Knowledge about breast feeding and duration of breast feeding

Variable	Breast feeding		Knowledge of breastfeeding		
	Frequency	Percentage	adequate knowledge	ANC source of knowledge	Knowledge of importance
Time of breastfeeding					
Immediately after birth	23	20.5	19(82.6%)	17(73.9%)	21(91.3%)
After 1 hour	37	33.0	35(94.6%)	19(51.4%)	32(86.5%)
After 2 hours	18	16.1	17(94.4%)	2(11.1%)	16(88.9%)
After 1 day	6	5.4	2(33.3%)	3(50%)	5(83.3%)
Others	28	25	19(67.9)	12(42.9%)	27(96.4%)
			93	53	101
Duration of exclusive breastfeeding					
<6 months	21	18.6	14(66.7%)	9(42.8%)	18(85.7%)
6 months	65	58.0	60(93.3%)	40(61.5)	63(96.9%)
>6 months	12	10.7	7(58.3%)	3(25%)	8(66.7%)
None	14	12.5	12(85.7%)	1(7.1%)	12(85.7%)
Length of breast feeding					
1-6 months	37	33	33(89.1%)	7(18.9%)	20(54.1%)
6-12 months	29	25.9	27(93.1%)	22(75.6%)	28(96.6%)
1-2 years	24	21.4	16(66.7%)	19(79.2%)	23(95.8%)
>2 years	5	4.5	2(40%)	4(80%)	3(60%)
Others	17	15.2	15(88.2%)	1(5.9%)	6(35.3%)

The study showed that majority of the mother's breastfeed their babies after one hour post-delivery 33.3%; 18.1% attended ANC, 27.2% attended 3-4 times and 70.2% had health education during ANC (Table 8). However, 20.5% of the mother's breastfed immediately and 91.3% attended ANC, 69.5% had attended 3-4 times and 95.6% had health education during ANC. However, 5.4% of the mothers' breastfed after one day post-delivery 50%, attended ANC, 33.3% attended 3 to 4 times and 16.7% got health education during ANC. The study also showed that 58.0% of the mothers breastfed their babies exclusively for six months and 86.2% attended ANC, 27.7% attended 3 to 4 times and 73.8% of

the mothers got health education, however, 18.6% of the mothers breast fed for less than six months; 52.4% of the mothers had attended ANC during pregnancy, 28.8% attended 3 to 4 times and 70.2% got health education. Also the study indicated that 10.7% of the mothers breastfed for more than six months; 50% attended ANC and 33% attended 3 to 4 times. Majority of the mothers breast fed for 1 to 6 months 33% and 18.9% of the mother attended ANC 3 to 4 times and 51.4% had health education. However, 51.7% of the mother's breast fed for six months to one year and 51.7% attended ANC, 27.6% attended 3 to 4 times and 86.8% got health education. (Table 5).

Table 5: ANC services and duration of breast feeding

Variable	Breast feeding		ANC services		
	Frequency	Percentage	Attending	Frequency	Education
Time of breastfeeding				3-4	
Immediately after birth	23	20.5	21(91.3%)	16(69.5%)	22(95.6%)
After 1 hour	37	33.0	30(18.1%)	10(27.2%)	26(70.2%)
After 2 hours	18	16.1	15(83.3%)	5(27.8%)	11(61.1%)
After 1 day	6	5.4	3(50%)	2(33.3%)	1(16.7%)
Others	28	25	13(46.4%)	4(14.2%)	17(60.7%)
			82	38	82
Duration of exclusive breastfeeding					
<6 months	21	18.6	11(52.4%)	6(28.8%)	15(71.4%)
6 months	65	58.0	56(86.2%)	18(27.7%)	48(73.8%)
>6 months	12	10.7	6(50%)	7(33.3%)	9(75%)
None	14	12.5	9(13.4%)	8(57.1%)	10(71.4%)
Length of breast feeding					
1-6 months	37	33	7(18.9%)	7(18.9%)	19(51.4%)
6-12 months	29	25.9	15(51.7%)	8(27.6%)	24(86.8%)
1-2 years	24	21.4	19(79.2%)	20(83.3%)	20(83.3%)
>2 years	5	4.5	3(60%)	3(60%)	5(100%)
Others	17	15.2	11(64.7%)	0	14(82.4%)

The study shows that 20.5% of the mothers breastfeed their babies immediately, the majority of which (39.1%) had small scale business, and 2.8% were house wives (Table 9). However, among those who breastfed their babies after one hour (33.0%), the majority had small scale businesses, and 8.1% were casual workers. The study also shows that 18.6% of mothers breastfed their babies exclusively for less than six months and the minority were casual workers with 14.3%. However, 58.0% of the mothers breast fed their babies exclusively for six months and majority were small scale business mothers 43.7% and 10.8% were casual workers and housewives. The study also shows that 33% of the mother's

breastfed their babies for period of 1 to 6 months and majority were small scale business mothers 29.7% and 6.3% were housewives however 25.9% of the mothers breastfed their babies between 6months to one years and majority 27.6% were peasants and 3.1% were house wives. And also indicates that 21.4% of the mother's breastfed for 1 to 2 years and majority 33.3% were housewives and 8.3% were casual workers.

The study also shows that 10.7% of the mothers breastfed 4 times and majority 41.7% were casual workers and 16.7% were peasants and housewives however 20.5% of the mothers breastfed 6times and majority 39.1% were casual workers and 4.35 were house wives. (Table 6).

Table 6: Mothers' occupation and duration of breast feeding

Variable	Breast feeding		Occupation			
	Frequency	Percentage	peasants	Casual workers	Small scale business	housewives
Time of breastfeeding						
Immediately after birth	23	20.5	8(34.8%)	4(17.4%)	9(39.1%)	2(8.7%)
After 1 hour	37	33.0	12(32.4%)	3(8.1%)	13(35.1%)	5(13.5%)
After 2 hours	18	16.1	5(27.8%)	1(5.6%)	7(38.9%)	4(22.2%)
After 1 day	6	5.4	0	3(50%)	5(83.3%)	2(33.3%)
Others	28	25	4(14.3%)	1(3.6%)	12(42.9%)	0
			29	13	46	13
Duration of exclusive breastfeeding						
<6 months	21	18.6	5(23.8%)	3(14.3%)	5(23.8%)	5(23.8%)
6 months	65	58.0	15(23.1%)	7(10.8%)	28(43.1%)	7(10.8%)
>6 months	12	10.7	5(41.7%)	1(8.3%)	6(50%)	0
None	14	12.5	4(28.6%)	2(14.3%)	7(50%)	1(7.1%)
Length of breast feeding						
1-6 months	37	33	9(24.3%)	5(13.5%)	11(29.7%)	2(6.3%)
6-12 months	29	25.9	8(27.6%)	3(10.3%)	18(62.1%)	1(3.4%)
1-2 years	24	21.4	6(25%)	2(8.3%)	7(29.2%)	8(33.3%)
>2 years	5	4.5	0	1(20%)	2(40%)	2(40%)
Others	17	15.2	6(35.3%)	3(17.6%)	8(47.1%)	0

The study shows that most mother breastfeed their babies after one hour 33.0% and majority where aged 24 to 34 years 21.6% and 13.5% where aged 35 to 44years however 20.5% breastfed their babies immediately and majority where aged 35 to 44years with 39.1% and the least where aged 15 to 24years with 13.0%. Also 5.4% of the mothers breastfed their babies after one day and 33.3% where aged between 25to34 years. The study also shows that 18.6% Of the mothers breastfed their babies exclusively for less than 6months and most of them where aged between 15 to24 years 33.3% and 14.3% where aged 45years and above however the study also indicated that 58.0% breastfed their babies for six months exclusively; 30.8% Of the mothers where

aged above 45years and 7.6% of the mothers where aged between 15 to 24 years. the study also indicates that majority of the mothers 33% breastfed their babies for 1 to 6 months and many24.3% where aged between 25 to 34years and 8.6 where aged between 35 to 44 years however 25.9% of those who breastfed for one to two years majority where aged between 15 to 35 years 17.2% and among those who breast fed 1 to 2 years majority 33.3% where aged between 25 to 34years.the study also shows that 10.7% breastfed 4times and 41.7% we aged 35 to 44 years and 16% were aged between 15 to 24zears however 20.5% breastfed their babies 6 times and majority where aged above 25 years.(Table 7).

Table 7: Age of mother and duration of breast feeding

Variable	Breast feeding		Age			
	Frequency	Percentage	15-24	25-34	35-44	≥45
Time of breastfeeding						
Immediately after birth	23	20.5	3(13.0%)	7(30.4%)	9(39.1%)	4(17.4%)
After 1 hour	37	33.0	6(16.2%)	8(21.6%)	5(13.5%)	6(16.2%)
After 2 hours	18	16.1	3(16.7%)	5(27.8%)	6(33.3%)	4(22.2%)
After 1 day	6	5.4	1(16.7%)	2(33.3%)	1(16.7%)	1(16.7%)
Others	28	25	4(14.3%)	3(10.7%)	8(28.6%)	10(35.7%)
			17	27	32	25
Duration of exclusive breastfeeding						
<6 months	21	18.6	7(33.3%)	6(28.5%)	5(23.8%)	3(14.3%)
6 months	65	58.0	5(7.6%)	11(16.9%)	19(29.3%)	20(30.8%)
>6 months	12	10.7	3(25%)	5(41.7%)	3(25%)	1(8.3%)
None	14	12.5	2(14.2%)	6(42.9%)	5(35.7%)	1(7.1%)
Length of breast feeding						
1-6 months	37	33	7(18.9%)	9(24.3%)	3(8.1%)	5(13.5%)
6-12 months	29	25.9	5(17.2%)	5(17.2%)	15(51.7%)	4(13.8%)
1-2 years	24	21.4	4(16.7%)	8(33.3%)	5(20.8%)	6(25%)
>2 years	5	4.5	1(20%)	2(40%)	1(20%)	1(20%)
Others	17	15.2	0	1(5.9)	3(17.6%)	4(23.5%)

The study shows that most mothers fed their babies (33%) an hour after delivery. However, 20.5% of the mothers' breast fed their babies immediately after delivery. Most mothers who breast fed their babies immediately after delivery had attained primary level education 30.4%. And 50% of those who breastfed their babies after one day had attained secondary level. The study also indicated that mothers exclusively breastfed their babies for less than six months 18.6% and 52.2% had attained tertiary level and 19.0% had informal education however the study

indicates that most mothers breast fed exclusively for six months 58.0% and most of the mothers had tertiary level. the study also shows that most mothers breastfed their babies for 1-6 months 33% and 56.7% of these mothers have primary level education and 19.4% had informal education however 25.9% breastfed for 6months to one year and majority had attained primary level 31.0% and 17.2% had tertiary level. And those who breast fed their babies for 1to 2years 21.4%; majority of them attained primary level.

Table 8: Mother's education status and duration of breast feeding

Variable	Breast feeding		Education level			
	Frequency	Percentage	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary	Informal
Time of breastfeeding						
Immediately after birth	23	20.5	7(30.4%)	5(21.7%)	7(30.4%)	2(8.7%)
After 1 hour	37	33.0	22(59.5%)	6(16.2%)	3(8.1%)	5(13.5%)
After 2 hours	18	16.1	5(27.8%)	7(38.9%)	1(5.6%)	2(11.1%)
After 1 day	6	5.4	1(16.7%)	3(50%)	0	2(10%)
Others	28	25	11(39.3%)	9(32.1%)	0	4(14.2%)
			46	30	11	16
Duration of exclusive breastfeeding						
<6 months	21	18.6	9(42.9%)	5(23.8%)	11(52.4%)	4(19.0%)
6 months	65	58.0	20(30.8%)	9(13.8%)	3(4.6%)	8(12.3%)
>6 months	12	10.7	6(50%)	5(41.7%)	7(58.3%)	1(8.3%)
None	14	12.5	11(78.6%)	1(7.1%)	1(7.1%)	3(21.4%)
Length of breast feeding						
1-6 months	37	33	21(56.7%)	11(29.7%)	3(8.1%)	1(2.7%)
6-12 months	29	25.9	9(31.0%)	7(24.1%)	5(17.2%)	8(9.8%)
1-2 years	24	21.4	7(29.2%)	5(20.8%)	2(9.5%)	4(16.7%)
>2 years	5	4.5	2(40%)	1(20%)	0	1(20%)
Others	17	15.2	7(41.2%)	8(47.1%)	0	2(11.8%)

DISCUSSION

The feed after one hour after birth and also most of them agreed that the baby is supposed to be breast fed for one to six months. The results further indicated that more participants accepted that the baby should be breast fed eight to twelve times a day. This was in agreement with the report released by UNICEF which clearly stated that it was recommended that all women should breastfeed their infants exclusively in the first six months, and subsequently with supplementary feeding for 2 years for optimal growth and development [14]. This is because Breast feeding is the normal method to provide infants with the nutrients they need for healthy growth and development [1].

The results show that parity is directly related to duration of breast feeding. Higher parity increases the duration of breastfeeding this is because mothers of high parity have long birth intervals compared to low parity and it also well established that parity is closely related to maternal age.

Mother who had the knowledge regarding the importance of exclusive breastfeeding and breastfeeding at large were likely to

adhere to exclusive breast feeding compared to those with limited knowledge on importance of exclusive breast feeding breastfeeding.

Furthermore, majority of the participants knew that breastfeeding helps in proper growth and development of the baby. This was in agreement with the report released by WHO, which stated that breast feeding provide infants with the nutrients they need for healthy growth and development [1].

The majority of the participants who had knowledge about breast feeding, most of them had got the information from ANC counseling. The results further indicated the more participants got health education and were counseled at the ANC. This is in agreement with research done by [27] where adequate counseling about breastfeeding during antenatal care improve breastfeeding. Antenatal attendance is a potential determinant of infant feeding practice [28]. Antenatal care increases the likelihood of early initiation of breast feeding [13]. Mothers who did not attend antenatal clinic during pregnancy have a poor initiation and exclusivity of

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breastfeeding [13]. However, other studies showed that mothers in Bemidji, obtained their knowledge about breastfeeding from different resources such as: Physicians, books or articles about breastfeeding, internet, and from mother to mother [29]. Health care providers should be aware that their own beliefs and attitudes toward breastfeeding may affect a woman's choice to breastfeed [29]. Mothers' trust their health care providers; therefore, care providers' opinions regarding a particular issue such as breastfeeding could be considered.

The implication here is that high qualities of counseling improve an adherence and long duration of breastfeeding [2]. A study carried out in Zambia reported that nursing mother who had received adequate counseling on breast feeding had a high rate of practicing breast feeding than those who don't, 58% to 70% respectively [30]. Also a study conducted in South Africa, Zambia and Zimbabwe indicated that high quality counseling improved adherence and long duration of exclusive breast feeding up to 6 months [30]. Improper practices such as introduction of pre-lacteal foods, rejection of colostrum, delayed initiation of breastfeeding' water intake during early months (within 5 months), and complementary feeding (within 5 months), might often significantly increase the risk of morbidity and mortality decrease milk intake and premature termination of breast feeding [31].

The study shows that most mothers exclusively breastfed their babies for a period of less than six months. The results also show that most mothers generally breastfed their babies up to 12 months. In this study the duration of exclusive breastfeeding and overall breastfeeding

The study shows that mothers who are not employed fully are most likely to adhere to breastfeeding than those who are fully employed. This is with similar studies related to exclusive breastfeeding and short overall breastfeeding [32]. Occupation limits the time mothers spend with their babies. This encourages complementary feeding (within 5 months), leading decreased milk intake and premature termination of breast feeding [31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40].

The study shows that mothers aged ≥ 25 years practiced longer duration of breastfeeding (39.1%) than the young ones (14.2%). This is in line with the results obtained by Kennedy-Stephenson, [33] in which timing and duration of breastfeeding improved with increased maternal age for all race-ethnicity groups. This implies that breast feeding is more in older women compared to young age group and therefore my study was in agreement with this report [35,36,37,38,39,40].

In the current study the majority of participants who were breast feeding and breast fed their babies immediately after delivery had attained primary level education. Also participants who had attained primary level education had a higher adherence to breastfeeding exclusively breast feeding for six months. This is similar to the study by [34], in which low level of maternal education was linked to lower breastfeeding rates.

was associated with parity, maternal age, occupation, education level, antenatal service and knowledge of mothers on breastfeeding.

CONCLUSION

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